

FCF011

DIFERENCES BETWEEN FERMENTED AND UNFERMENTED BIFIDO MILK INTAKE IN GUT MORPHOLOGY OF BALB/c MICE

CRISTINA STEWART BITTENCOURT BOGSAN (PG), MARICÊ NOGUEIRA DE OLIVEIRA

Department of Biochemical – Pharmaceutical Technology, FCF/USP

Introduction and Objectives: The increasing in life expectancy, high cost of health care, and desire of live quality are stimulating the research and development of new functional foods. Differences between fermented and unfermented bifido milk intake in gut morphology of Balb/c mice were investigated.

Material and Methods: Three bifido milks were prepared with *Bifidobacterium animalis* subsp. *lactis* HN019: bifido fermented milk (BFM), bifido fermented milk than pasteurized (BFMP), and milk added with bifido (BNFM). Milk and water were used as control. Enumerations of bifidobacteria were determined during storage of all products at 4 °C. Balb/c mice were allocated between five different groups than fed with commercial food and bifido milk for two weeks *ad libitum*, than sacrificed in CO₂ chamber. The colon was sectioned and the histology was analyzed using hematoxilin-eosin (HE) and ocean blue (OB) stain by light microscopy and digitally processed using photometrics methodology.

Results and Conclusions: Four different areas were considered, and percentages of threshold areas were calculated. Mean values were compared using the Tukey test ($P \leq 0.05$). Counts of bifidobacteria were higher than $9.00 \log_{10} \text{CFU/mL}^{-1}$ for all products. The digital images of HE and OB laminas respectively shown that controls water ($19.40\% \pm 3.25$; $24.79\% \pm 3.39$) and milk ($17.55\% \pm 5.26$; $32.31\% \pm 3.14$), and BNFM ($28.61\% \pm 5.28$; $24.01\% \pm 3.76$) have significantly similar cellular infiltrate and lower threshold areas than that observed in BFM ($36.90\% \pm 5.97$; $42.56\% \pm 4.96$) and BFMP ($31.29\% \pm 4.83$; $37.25\% \pm 4.32$). These data suggest that metabolites produced by bifido fermentation, and not just its intake is key in protecting the host gut mucosa throughout increase in mucus production and establishing a low-grade inflammation.

Financing: FAPESP; CNPq

FCF012

ANALYSIS OF TOTAL HARDNESS OF WATER FROM PUBLIC SUPPLY OF EIGHT COUNTIES IN THE SOUTHERN REGION OF BAHIA

JULIANO OLIVEIRA SANTANA (IC), FERNANDA LUIZA ANDRADE DE AZEVEDO (IC), ISAAC PARAÍSO RAMETH DE ALMEIDA (IC), IVON PINHEIRO LÔBO (PG)

Faculty of Pharmacy, UNIME-Itabuna

Introduction and Objectives: The hardness of water is caused essentially by the presence of calcium and magnesium that are really important data used to assess their quality. When hard water is present in high range, removing the ions of hardness is necessary, because the hard water causes a number of drawbacks: it is unpalatable, spends much soap to form foam, salt deposits on equipment and crockery smear. Thus through the process of titrimetric analysis, we decided to determine the total hardness of the public distribution network in eight cities in the southern region of Bahia, the method of titration with EDTA.

Material and Methods: The investigations were carried out on eight cities in the southern region: Buerarema, Camacan, Itabuna, Itapé, Itajuípe, Ilhéus, Mascote e Ubaitaba. The water used in the experiment were collected in amber bottles directly from the taps from the residential public supply network and analyzed in the laboratory of Analytical Chemistry of the Metropolitan Union of Education and Culture - UNIME. The method used for analysis of analyte was the titrimetry of complexation using the standardized solution of EDTA, each sample titrated in triplicate.

Results and Conclusions: The indices of total water hardness in the eight cities examined were: 3.168 mg/L (Camacan); 5.148 mg/L (Mascote); 16.633 mg/L (Buerarema); 29.307 mg/L (Ubaitaba); 36.435 mg/L (Itajuípe); 43.168 mg/L (Itabuna); 46.732 mg/L (Ilhéus) and 127.524 mg/L de CaCO₃ (Itapé). According to the decree No. 1469 of December 29, 2000 the Ministry of Health CaCO₃ content may not exceed 500 mg / L, therefore, with respect to the parameter analyzed, the water coming out of the taps of the municipalities is analyzed fit for consumption.

Financing: UNIME-Itabuna